

DEVELOPMENT OF DISTANCE EDUCATION IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: The article provides information on Digitization in Higher Education Institutions and its creation of new opportunities for education and management, data collection and analysis, cooperation and communication.

Key words: digitization, online education, interactive, distance education, westlaw, lexisnexis, jstor.

The characteristics of the educational process in higher educational institutions, as well as the importance of universities in society and economy, are changing rapidly. All over the world, universities are competing with each other to attract students, teachers and financial resources. In such a competition, higher education institutions that keep up with the times and use new digital opportunities are gaining an advantage over others.

Digitization has created new opportunities for learning and management, facilitating data collection and analysis, collaboration and communication. The benefits of digitization include increased productivity, increased student engagement, personalized learning, and the use of new teaching methods. In addition, digitization facilitates the management of universities, curricula, faculty, staff, and resources. One of the key benefits of digitization is the potential for increased student engagement. { 1} Using digital tools such as online learning platforms, social media, and mobile apps, universities can create interactive and engaging learning experiences that keep students motivated and on track. Also, digitization allows universities to use new teaching methods such as games and virtual reality.

These methods can be used to create an interactive learning experience that makes it easier for students to understand complex concepts and theories. Increase student acquisition rates, increase employability by building the necessary competencies, and deliver information through various media and tools. By increasing the prestige of universities that use explanatory methods and creating conditions for them to get additional benefits through these opportunities, a relative advantage over others is formed.

In particular, in the decree of the President of our country on April 29, 2020 "On additional measures for the fundamental improvement of legal education and science in the Republic of Uzbekistan", the priority directions of further development of legal education and science among them, the task of creating an open, transparent, subjectivity-free and abuse-free educational environment by introducing the "Electronic University" (E-University) system is indicated.

{2} Based on this, systematic work was carried out at the Tashkent State Law University, and a number of electronic systems were developed and implemented. In particular, the possibility of electronic application on any issue was created for students, and a special Student Service Center was introduced, which operates on the basis of the single window principle, an electronic system for the selection of graduate qualification works and master's theses, and scientific supervisors was created, the electronic payment contract was created. The mechanism of online monitoring of receipts and payment arrears was launched. The main result related to the educational process was the introduction of a distance learning platform and an electronic evaluation system. Although the university's distance learning platform (<http://distant.tsul.uz>) is based on the world-renowned Moodle (object-oriented dynamic learning environment), this system has been significantly improved. . In particular, video chat (Big Blue Button) and Zoom software for conducting lecture sessions, mechanisms for handing over control work and passing them through the anti-plagiarism system were integrated, more than 21 thousand electronic contents (video lecture, audio, electronic reports, case materials) were placed.

Also, the assessment process has become completely transparent, in which control works are submitted and evaluated through an electronic system. In this system, the control written work is submitted by the student in electronic form, that is, it is uploaded to the system, then it is automatically encrypted and sent to the appropriate department for verification in electronic form.

In the departments, these works are distributed among professors and teachers, and the system itself is checked, evaluated, and a review is written on the given grade, that is, it is shown why it was evaluated in this way and what shortcomings the student made. The grade of the checked work and the written review of the work can be seen in the student's personal office. In addition, the university electronic library has been established and more than 10 thousand sources have been placed in it, and the complete digitization of existing literature is ongoing.

Access to international resources by connecting to international databases such as WestLaw, LexisNexis and JSTOR for lawyers. From a management perspective, digitization makes it easier for universities to manage their resources and academic programs. For example, digital tools can be used to manage student learning, track faculty and staff performance, and allocate resources efficiently.

At the same time, digitization work at the Tashkent State Law University is being continued, work is being carried out on the introduction of the electronic management system of the independent university (E-University), the attendance system of students through automatic special cameras. It should be noted that now students are much more is different.

Now they have modern demands and needs, and the providers of modern higher education services should be worthy of them. Today, according to the main demand of the time, educational organizations, especially higher education organizations, should rely on new technologies such as flexible learning, artificial intelligence, UX-design, virtual or cyberspace in the development of their activities. , augmented reality.

{3} At this point, it is necessary for higher education organizations to gradually move to the concept described as "University 4.0", in some cases "digital university" or "smart university". Therefore, a modern digital university offers convenient opportunities that help students and teachers organize the teaching process and communications, automate digital recording and analysis without bureaucracy, competently design individual educational trajectories, and quickly respond to possible problems. and should provide services.

In essence, all related processes of a modern university should be established on the basis of digital technologies. This requires a shift from the analysis of work with applicants, the study process and the quality of education to the management of large volumes of data, ending with the monitoring of graduate employment and promotion.

Today, the systematic and consistent reforms in the field of education in our country are showing their results, our universities have achieved academic and financial independence, set their goals and objectives, adapt to the requirements of the times, and train highly qualified personnel for today and the future. has a chance.

At the same time, the continuation of the implemented reforms, the implementation of the laws and regulations adopted by the educational organizations and the priority tasks in the higher education system indicated by

the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan will ensure the high quality of education in our country. serves to reach heights and, most importantly, to develop our young people into highly qualified personnel who can be competitive at the international level.

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